

Enhancing the Value of Native Breeds: Quality Keys

www.af4eu.eu

Greek breed cows grazing in silvopastoral systems of Evgritania

During the 20th century, farmers struggled to replace their animals with improved breeds with very high milk and meat yields. However, high yielding animals are generally more susceptible to metabolic diseases and have very high feeding requirements. Thus, producers are slowly turning to indigenous breeds of livestock, which are not high yielding but are resistant to extreme conditions, very high or low temperatures, water scarcity, excessively humid climates, poor vegetation, high altitudes and steep slopes.

Adding value to local livestock breeds is an excellent way to promote sustainability, preserve cultural heritage and improve biodiversity. Local breeds - those that have evolved over centuries in a particular region - often have unique characteristics that make them resilient and well adapted to local conditions.

Local breeds are usually more resistant to parasitic, infectious and metabolic diseases than external commercial breeds. As a result, local breeds maximise the use of their habitats and, over time, contribute to shaping the specific rural landscape, especially in mountainous areas. This adaptability leads to relatively low yields but also to products of unique quality and low production costs.

Enhancing their added value requires a commitment to both improving their quality and making them more attractive to markets. Milk and meat from local breeds usually have a better fatty acid profile, higher oxidative stability, pleasant aroma and taste. These products form the basis of many traditional recipes and local products (cheeses, yoghurts, sausages, etc.) of high quality and commercial value. The expectations and objectives of producers and consumers can be brought together so that the high demand for quality products can act as an incentive for the development of rural livestock farming and the preservation of the wealth of local breeds. The result will be to supply local markets and cities with high-value products and ensure a satisfactory income for producers.

**Georgios Mpakogiorgos (veterinary),
Anastasia Pantera**

Department of forestry & Natural Environment Management, Karpenissi, Greece

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.